

METHODOLOGY FOR IMPROVING PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF BIOLOGY TEACHERS

Sharipova Farida Salimjanovna

Assistant, Termez Branch of Tashkent Medical Academy

Kongirotova Anorhol Inoyatovna

Assistant, Termez Branch of Tashkent Medical Academy

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Abstract. Updating the content of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, modernizing the organization of the educational process of professors and teachers working in the educational system in the era of globalization of information, updating the methodical knowledge, skills and qualifications of applying innovative technologies to this process is one of the urgent problems of today. To modernize the organization of the educational process of professors and teachers working in higher educational institutions, to activate the cognitive activity of students, to achieve educational efficiency by creating an educational-methodical complex, electronic textbooks, a bank of non-standard adaptive tests, a syllabus for educational courses, which prepares the ground for appropriate organization Development and renewal of methodological knowledge, skills and qualifications necessary for education, raising them to the level of state requirements and world education standards is one of the main issues of the reform period. On February 16, 2006, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan Resolution No. 25 "On the Retraining of Pedagogical Personnel and Further Improvement of Their Qualification System", "Regulation on the Retraining of Pedagogical Personnel" requires a great deal of attention to be paid to the training of pedagogic staff of higher educational institutions. and set special tasks for retraining institutions.

Keywords: technique, tool, method, basis, reforms.

МЕТОДИКА СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЯ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ ПОДГОТОВКИ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ БИОЛОГИИ

Аннотация. Обновление содержания системы высшего образования Республики Узбекистан, модернизация организации образовательного процесса профессорско-преподавательского состава, работающих в системе образования в эпоху глобализации информации, обновление методических знаний, навыков и квалификации применения инновационных технологий к этому процессу является одной из актуальных проблем современности. Модернизировать организацию учебного процесса профессорско-преподавательского состава, работающих в высших учебных заведениях, активизировать познавательную деятельность студентов, добиться эффективности обучения за счет создания учебно-методического комплекса, электронных учебников, банка нестандартных адаптационных тестов, программу учебных курсов, которая подготавливает почву для соответствующей организации. Развитие и обновление методических знаний, умений и навыков, необходимых для образования, доведение их до уровня государственных требований и мировых образовательных стандартов является одним из основных вопросов периода реформ. Постановление Кабинета Министров Республики Узбекистан от 16 февраля 2006 года № 25 «О переподготовке педагогических кадров и дальнейшем совершенствовании системы их квалификации», «Положение о переподготовке педагогических кадров» требует большого внимания направить на

подготовку педагогических кадров высших учебных заведений. и поставить специальные задачи перед учреждениями переподготовки.

Ключевые слова: техника, инструмент, метод, основа, реформы.

INTRODUCTION

The main goal of the program is the development of training based on innovative technologies that meet the requirements of the times in biological sciences and training in the design of technological maps.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

"Brainstorming" method is a method that collects free opinions and opinions expressed by students on a problem and comes to a certain solution through them. There are written and oral forms of brainstorming. In oral form, each student expresses his or her opinion to a question posed by the teacher. Learners state their answers clearly and concisely. In the written form, learners write their answers to the given question on paper cards in a short and visible way. Answers are attached to the board (using magnets) or pinboard (using pins). In the written form of the "Brainstorming" method, there is an opportunity to group the answers by certain characters. This method, when used correctly and positively, teaches a person to think freely, creatively and non-standardly. When using the "Brainstorming" method, there is an opportunity to involve all learners, including the formation of a culture of communication and discussion among learners. Learners develop the ability to express their thoughts not only verbally, but also in writing, logical and systematic thinking. The lack of evaluation of the expressed opinions leads to the formation of different ideas in the learners. This method serves to develop creative thinking in students.

The "Brainstorming" method is implemented depending on the goal set by the teacher:

1. When the goal is to determine the basic knowledge of learners, this method is implemented in the introductory part of the lesson.
2. When the goal is to repeat the topic or connect one topic with the next topic, it is done in the transition to a new topic.
3. Consolidation of the learned topic is carried out in the reinforcement part of the lesson after the targeted topic.

"Role-playing" method is a method by which learners demonstrate various conditions of life situations by staging. Role-playing games differ from business games in that there is no evaluation. At the same time, in the "Role-playing" method, learners are satisfied with playing roles in the scenario developed by the teacher, while in the "Working game" method, role-players independently decide what tasks should be performed in a given situation. In the role-playing game, participants actively work together to solve the problem, like a business game. Role-playing games develop interpersonal skills in learners. In the "role play" method, the teacher should have prior knowledge about the students. Because the individual character and behavior of each learner is important in playing roles. The topics chosen should be appropriate to the level of mastery of the learners. Role-playing games help to motivate learners in the learning process.

RESULTS

It is known that each stage of the development of the state and society, based on the social, economic, scientific-technical, spiritual-educational and cultural needs of the individual,

society and the state, puts certain state and social orders in front of the educational system in accordance with the methodological principle of historical and logical unity of didactics. After the independence of our republic, education was defined as a priority direction in the social sphere, the "Law on Education" and "National Program of Personnel Training", which are the methodological and theoretical basis for the introduction of higher education, provided for a higher education system that has matured in all respects, adapted to life in society, education and State orders have been placed, such as the creation of socio-political, legal, psychological-pedagogical and other conditions, and the education of citizens who feel their responsibility towards society, state and family, who have consciously chosen professional programs and then mastered them thoroughly. The booklet "National Idea: Basic Concept and Principles" created taking into account the socio-economic, ideological, spiritual-educational changes taking place in our society, and the principles of building a legal-democratic society, puts social orders before the educational system.

DISCUSSION

It is not for nothing that the 21st century is called the century of "Biology", because here the achievements based on the main processes and components of human life are embodied before our eyes. No matter how many achievements and discoveries are made in the fields of biology, still a quarter of humanity lives in poverty and hunger. While technological advances are advancing, global challenges are being faced. Biological science suggests that these problems can be avoided and reduced in order to achieve food security, thereby meeting the needs for fuel, fiber and livestock (Teng, 2007a). In the 1990s, a major interest in biobusiness grew in Asia, a process that accelerated the development of pharmaceuticals and equipment manufacturing in exchange for rapid advances in biotechnology.

CONCLUSIONS

Indeed, many countries have secured primary entry gains and the limits of achievement have been set, this competitiveness reflected in large multinational companies and industrialized countries. In countries such as Singapore, core capacity has been driven by multibillion-dollar investments, which have led to the development of biomedical sectors. Gurinder S. Shahi's (2004, Pearson Education South Asia Pearson.) Bioentrepreneurship in Asia notes that bioentrepreneurship is not well developed in many Asian countries. The Asian financial crisis that began in 1996-1997 is still ongoing, necessitating the need for new businesses in some cases. In Thailand, the Royal Family's food program was self-sufficient; In Malaysia, national plans have been developed, which are based on the management of agriculture.¹³ In China, this process continues economic growth based on the living standards of the people, and this is linked to the guaranteed supply of food, fiber and fuel. As the last peak, crude oil valuations affected the booming economy in Asian markets, followed by cost recovery in bioscience enterprises (Teng, 2007a).

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